

FACE RECOGNITION USING DEEP CONVOLUTIONAL NEURAL NETWORKS: A SURVEY

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ABSTRACT

Face recognition technology uses Deep Convolutional Neural Network (DCNN) to extract biometric features for identity authentication. It has been used in various application domains, including military, law enforcement, finance, public security, and other daily life applications. This paper reviews the updated progress of DCNN architectures used for face recognition. It also explores pretrained models along with training datasets that exist. Furthermore, some face recognition applications are summarized. The limitations and further research directions are pointed. Although face recognition is an emerging technique, it raises security concerns.

KEYWORDS

Face Recognition, Deep Face, Deep CNN

1. INTRODUCTION

Face recognition (FR) technology identifies or verifies faces in a static image, video data, and data stream. FR consists of four processes: face detection, alignment, feature extraction, and feature matching Almadby and Elrefaei (2019); Jain and Li (2011); Masi et al. (2018). Figure 1 illustrates the flow of these processes. Face detection locates a face in an image and marks it with a bounding box, determining the face location, size, and pose. Face alignment normalizes the face to be consistent with coordinates (i.e., photometric). Feature extraction extracts essential information (i.e., feature vector) from the face. The feature vector is required for the feature matching process. Feature matching performs matching feature vectors against one or more known faces in a prepared database. Overall, the FR produces a face identification (so-called FaceID) that exists in the faces' database or does not exist, which refers to an unknown person.

Figure 1. Face Recognition Processes Pipeline

FR technology has been used in various application domains Adjabi et al. (2020); Ali et al. (2021). It is used in law enforcement as police officers instantly identify individuals in the field. Forensic investigations automatically recognize individuals in security footage or other videos. It can also be utilized to find missing children and victims of human trafficking. FR is used in social media applications. For instance, Facebook automatically recognizes members appearing in photos. It is practical for users to locate photos they are in and suggest when particular people should be tagged in photos. It helps the blind person by alerting with a vibration when people are smiling, for example. FR is used in finance. It is currently being used at ATMs to protect people's identities. FR is used in other daily life applications. Smartphones are now using FR to unlock phones. Airlines have already started using FR to help people check bags, check into flights, and board planes faster.

Restaurants use FR as customers place orders through a digital menu and then use face scan as a payment option. FR is used to control restricted access areas. It ensures that only authorized individuals get into facilities like labs, boardrooms, bank vaults, and other sensitive locations.

This survey presents a classification scheme that categorizes the literature on face recognition. It then classifies a set of related articles that were recently published into sub-categories according to specific criteria. The survey explains each sub-category. It also discusses the limitations of face recognition along with points to future research directions.

The rest of this paper is organized as follows. Section 2 introduces the classification scheme used to categorize the FR literature into subsets. In section 3, different Deep CNN network architectures are presented. Section 4 presents various pretrained models and section and section 5 presents the training datasets. Section 6 classifies face recognition applications. In section 7, the limitations of face recognition technology and further research directions are discussed. Section 8 concludes this paper and clarifies the findings.

2. LITERATURE CLASSIFICATION SCHEME

We built a new classification scheme to filter the literature on face recognition and categorize it into subcategories. The classification scheme is designed based on various characteristics that are extracted from the surveys recently published.

Figure 2. Face Recognition Literature Classification Scheme

As illustrated in Figure 2, the FR literature classification scheme consists of four main categories: DCNN Architectures, Pretrained Models, Training Datasets, and FR Applications. Each includes two sub-categories. The Deep CNN architectures are classified as classical networks, and modern networks Ali et al. (2021); Khan et al. (2020). Classical networks utilize stacked convolutional layers, while the modern networks explore novel approaches for constructing convolutional layers to increase learning efficiency. A Pretrained model is a DCNN model previously trained for face recognition on large benchmark datasets. Based on the DCNN architecture used to train a model, the Pretrained models are grouped into the backbone-based and assembled models. The backbone model uses a single network to extract features from an input image, while the assembled-based model uses multiple networks that are assembled for features extraction Ali et al (2021); Gwyn et al. (2021). The training datasets are classified into two types, depth, and breadth datasets Hupont and Fernandez (2019). The depth datasets contain many images per subject, usually more than 30 images on average per subject. In contrast, the breadth datasets include many subjects but fewer images per subject. The FR applications are grouped into verification and identification applications. The verification application matches face information to registered facial data to determine whether the two faces are of the same identity. It is the process of asking, “are you who you say you are?” The identification application compares face information to a database of identities to match it and discover its identity. It is the process of asking, “who are you?”

The classification scheme is applied to a set of 24 publications published from 2019 to early 2023. These publications include conference papers and journal articles. Books were ignored unless they were used for terms definition. The FR literature targeted in this survey covers novel contributions, extended work, and other surveys. The following sections explore each group of the publications and organize them based on the contributions and findings provided.

3. DEEP CNN ARCHITECTURES

A neural network includes three layers: input, hidden, and output. The input layer initializes data for the neural network Gulli and Pal (2017). The hidden layers, intermediate layers between the input and output layer, simultaneously perform multiple mathematical functions (i.e., activation functions) to map the values from one layer to the next. The output layer produces the result for given inputs. The neural network also consists of a function (so-called loss function) that minimizes the error, which is the difference between actual and predicted values Gulli and Pal (2017). A simple neural network consists of only one hidden layer (so-called a shallow neural network), while a deep neural network uses a cascade of multiple hidden layers of processing units for feature extraction and transformation Elhassouny and Smarandache (2019); Gulli and Pal (2017).

A Convolutional neural network (i.e., ConvNet or CNN) is a deep neural network. Besides input and output layers, CNN includes three main layers: convolutional, pooling, and fully connected layers. The convolutional layer is the essential building block of a CNN. The first layer represents a set of neurons (i.e., kernels) that receive data from the input layer and map the data to convolutional layers. The convolutional layers are supported by either additional convolutional or pooling layers. The convolutional layers shrink as they become deeper, primarily by divisible input factors. The last layers are fully connected layers that pass on the data to the output layer Albawi et al. (2017); Elhassouny and Smarandache (2019); Gulli and Pal (2017). The CNN depth refers to the number of layers, convolutional, pooling, and other layers, while the CNN width refers to the number of parameters the CNN carries out.

Table 1. Deep CNN Architectures

CNN Architecture	Reference	Width	Depth	Activation Function	Loss Function
Classic	Radman et al. (2022)	1728	25	ReLU	CE
	Ben Fredj et al. (2021)	2.7k	21	ReLU	Softmax
	Boyd et al. (2023)	14400	11	ReLU	CE
Modern	Ketab et al. (2023)	23328	14	ReLU	CE
	Niu et al. (2021)	2304	14	Maxout	Log
	Brown (2022)	50176	26	ReLU	Softmax

Table 1 classifies the DCNN architectures used for face recognition into classical networks and modern networks. Classical networks are stacked convolutional layers, while modern networks whose convolutional layers are constructed in many ways to improve learning efficiency. Table 1 also describes the DCNN's width and depth along with the activation and loss functions used. The activation function is set either at the end of or between neural networks. It supports determining if the neuron would fire or not. Several types of activation functions exist, including Sigmoid, hyperbolic tangent (tanh), Rectified Linear Units (ReLU), Leaky ReLU, and Exponential Linear Unit (ELU) Nwankpa et al. (2018). For layer minimization, several types of loss functions exist, including Mean Squared Error (MSE), Softmax, Cross-Entropy (CE), and Binary Cross-Entropy (BCE) Srivastava et al. (2019). Table 1 shows that most of the architectures use the ReLU activation function and CE loss function, while the Softmax loss function is barely used. It also shows that a loss function can be developed for specific purposes. For instance, in Niu et al. (2021), the authors try to maximize the values to eliminate the influence of noise signals in the image. Thus, they used the Maxout activation function and developed a specific loss function using a logarithmic equation for prediction loss.

3.1 Classical Networks

Radman et al. (2022) design a deep residual neural network (i.e., DResNet), a type of DCNN, to handle a forensic face sketch synthesis. ResNet learns a deep mapping between photos and sketches. The DResNet contains nine stacked residual blocks, and each consists of convolutional, batch normalization, and rectified-linear unit (ReLU) layers. The input and output layer does not have batch normalization; as a result, the network's depth is 25 layers. The DResNet uses 64 filters of size 3x3x64 that allow 64 feature maps, limiting its width to 1728 parameters. It also uses the Cross-Entropy loss function. An experiment was conducted on the network to train a model. For training, the authors used 699480 photo-sketch patch pairs from

three datasets (CUHK, AR, and the XM2VTS database). The results show that DResNet outperforms other existing models for face sketch recognition. The proposed DResNet achieves an average of 0.40% Visual Information Fidelity (VIF) scores over others. Overall, the proposed DResNet presents robustness to handle forensic photos, which validates the potential value of the DResNet for real applications.

Ben Fredj et al. (2021) present a DCNN to learn robust face verification in an unconstrained environment using large-scale data with a massive noisy and occluded face. The DCNN was built based on GoogLeNet style Inception models. It consists of 21 layers, including 3 convolutional and 18 Inception layers. It uses the ReLU activation function and Softmax loss function. The DCNN provides 2.7k parameters. For verification, experiments were conducted on the Labeled Faces in the Wild (LFW), which contains 13,233 images of 5749 people, and YouTube face (YTF), containing 3425 videos of 1595 different people. The results show that the trained model reaches the classification rate of 94.5% on LFW and the face recognition accuracy of 97.7%. Overall, the proposed DCNN achieves comparable performances on LFW and YTF for face verification.

Boyd et al. (2023) propose a DCNN to handle real-time face recognition. They use the Open-Source Neural Network library (Keras running on top of Tensorflow) to build the network. The proposed DCNN consists of 11 layers, including 3 convolutional, 2 max pooling, 3 dropouts, 1 flatten, and 2 dense layers. It uses the ReLU activation function and the Cross-Entropy (CE) loss function and handles 14400 parameters. The process first starts with a real-time input image captured from a camera, and then it is fed to the Viola-Jones algorithm for face detection. The face image is then converted into grayscale, resized to 120×120 pixels, and fed to the first convolution layer comprising 32 filters of size 3×3 pixels. A performance evaluation was conducted using a standard AT&T dataset containing 10 images from 40 individuals, leading to 400 images. Out of 400 images, 320 images (8 images from 40 individuals) were used for training and the remaining 80 images for testing. The result shows that the proposed DCNN reaches maximum recognition accuracy of 98.75%. The authors offer that the DCNN can be adapted to various applications such as face detection-based home automation, device control, attendance system, and intruder detection.

3.2 Modern Networks

Ketab et al. (2023) propose a DCNN to deal with low resolution face recognition. DCNN architecture has two branches. One projects high-resolution images to space, and the other one maps low-resolution images into space. The proposed DCNN architecture consists of 14 layers, including 10 convolutional and 4 max-pooling layers. It uses the ReLU activation, Cross-Entropy (CE) loss functions, and handles 23328 parameters. The DCNN was used to train a model of over 90,800 face images with variations in pose, expression, illumination, and age. An experiment was conducted on FERET, LFW, and MBGC datasets for evaluation. The proposed DCNN shows significant improvement and robustness against expression, illumination, and age variations. It outperforms competing methods across various resolutions of probe images. It shows significant performance improvement (5%) when applied to low-resolution images. The proposed method shows the reliable performance when faces are in the wild and taken by surveillance cameras.

Niu et al. (2021) introduce multiscale fusion lightweight convolution neural network for hyperspectral face recognition. Hyperspectral imaging combines traditional imaging and spectroscopy technologies to acquire spatial and spectral information for robust face recognition; however, the structure of hyperspectral images is more complicated than ordinary grayscale or RGB images. The proposed DCNN has a depth of 15 layers, integrating 5 convolution layers, 3 Network in Network (NIN) layers, 5 Second-Order Efficient Channel Attention (SECA) models, Max-Feature-Map layer, and max-pooling layer. It uses the Maxout activation, logarithmic loss functions and handles 2304 parameters. An experimental evaluation was conducted on three benchmark hyperspectral face databases, PolyU, CMU, and UWA. The results show that the proposed DCNN has achieved competitive accuracy and efficiency, significantly reducing storage space and computation overheads. These characteristics also show its broad applicability on the edge and mobile devices.

Brown (2022) proposes a DCNN of a bimodal system for enhancing security. The DCNN processes face and iris biometrics from a single image. The author uses the OpenCV library to build the network. The DCNN architecture consists of 26 layers, including 4 convolutional, 6 batch normalizations, 4 activations, 2 max-pooling, 3 dropouts, 2 dense, 1 input, 1 random translation, 1 resizing, and 1 flatten layer. It uses the ReLU activation, Cross-Entropy (CE) loss functions, and handles 50176 parameters. An experiment was conducted on IITD-Iris and CASIA-Iris-Distance datasets for evaluation. The result indicates that a smaller designed CNN achieves impressive results on challenging iris data. It shows that the proposed DCNN effectively outperforms other approaches.

4. PRETRAINED MODELS

A Pre-trained model is a DCNN that had been trained on a large dataset. The Pretrained models are classified based on the DCNN architectures used for training into the backbone-based and assembled models. The backbone architecture consists of a single network to extract features from an input image, while the assembled-based architecture has multiple networks that are assembled for features extraction Ali et al. (2021); Gwyn et al. (2021). Lots of pretrained models are available. However, the survey covers the modern models that trained using popular CNN architectures, including VGG19, ResNet50, Inception-v3 (GoogLeNet), EfficientNet-B3, and MobileFaceNet. The pretrained model is evaluated according to the challenge it deals with and the classification accuracy. The classification accuracy is the rate of correct predictions to the total number of input samples Mahdianpari et al. (2018).

Table 2 shows that pretrained models that deal with simple face challenges such as prediction accuracy and Thermal images achieve high classification accuracy (above 90%). The models exploited for complex challenges such as facial emotion, masked face, and preference prediction reach low classification accuracy (below 70%). Preference prediction relates to the process mobile device gallery of photos and videos and predicts preferences based on scene recognition, object detection, and facial analysis. In general, pretrained models provide acceptable results when used as they have been trained. Otherwise, they must be retrained or transferred to learn to handle challenges that they did not train for, which require specific datasets.

Table 2. Deep CNN Pretrained Models

Architecture Based	Reference	Model Name	Challenge	Accuracy
Backbone	Singh et al. (2022)	VGG19	Facial Emotion	69.10%
	Cheng et al. (2023)	FaceNet	Masked Face	93.00%
Assembled	Anand et al. (2020)	Inception-v3	Prediction Accuracy	91.43%
	Chen and Ross (2019)	Mobile-FaceNet	Thermal Image	99.30%
	Savchenko et al. (2022)	EfficientNet-B3	Preference Prediction	63.82%

4.1 Backbone

Singh et al. (2022) use VGG19 pretrained model to recognize facial emotions such as anger, disgust, fear, happiness, sadness, surprise, and neutral. VGG19 was built by the University of Oxford and trained on more than 1 million images from the ImageNet database and can classify up to 1000 objects. The authors run the VGG19 model against the Face Expression Recognition dataset (FER2013) that contains 35,887 various images with emotions for evaluation. The authors observed that the size of the dataset plays a vital role in facial expression recognition. The VGG19 model achieved better accuracy on facial emotions with more samples, such as happy, neutral, and angry, than other emotions.

Cheng et al. (2023) utilize ResNet-50 to identify people with face-masks due COVID-19 mandatory of use face masks. The ResNet-50 was built by the Microsoft Corporation and trained on the ImageNet database. The authors run the ResNet-50 model against the Real-world masked face recognition dataset (RMFRD) that contains 5000 masked faces of 525 people and 90000 unmasked faces for evaluation. The model has been more trained on unmasked faces than the masked faces dataset. Thus, the results show that the ResNet-50 model did better on the masked than on the masked dataset. The ResNet-50 model achieved an accuracy of 89.7016% for unmasked faces while 47.91% for masked faces.

4.2 Assembled

Anand et al. (2020) create a new dataset to train the Inception-v3 (GoogleNet) model to achieve higher accuracy. The Inception-v3 was built by the Google Corporation and trained on the ImageNet database. The authors created the dataset based on two principles, provide as many unique faces as possible and provide the maximum number of faces for everyone. They use the transfer learning method to increase the model training level. The transfer learning is done by adjusting the weight of the fully connected layers in the inception

model with the new dataset. The results show improvement for the recognition accuracy reaching 91.43%. The authors indicate that transfer learning a model over many datasets enhances its performance and accuracy.

Chen and Ross (2019) challenge matching face images obtained in the thermal spectrum with those obtained in the visible spectrum. They experiment with the MobileFaceNet model against multispectral face datasets, Pinellas County Sheriff’s Office (PCSO), and Army Research Laboratory (ARL) datasets. The PCSO and ARL datasets consist of face images acquired in the middle-wave infrared (MWIR) and long-wave infrared (LWIR) spectra. The MobileFaceNet model was developed by the School of Computer and Information Technology, Beijing University, trained on the CASIA-Webface dataset. The experimental results show that the MobileFaceNet model effectively synthesizes the visible spectrum images from thermal spectrum images and enhances cross-spectral face matching accuracy. The face matching accuracy reaches 99.30%. Nevertheless, the PCSO and ARL datasets are small; thus, further investigation is required to experiment with the MobileFaceNet model on a large-scale dataset.

Savchenko et al. (2022) use the EfficientNet-B3 model preferences prediction that processes mobile device gallery of photos and videos predict preferences of hobbies and lifestyle. Preferences prediction is based on scene recognition, object detection, and facial analysis. The Inception-v3 was built and released by the Google Corporation in 2019 Tan and Le (2019). The authors experimented with the Inception-v3 model on Photo Event Collection and Web Image Datasets for Event Recognition and Amazon Fashion data. The experimental results of the model reach a prediction accuracy of 63.82%. The authors provided the implementation publicly as Android application various personalized mobile services such as target advertisements, marketing, and recommender systems.

5. TRAINING DATASETS

The datasets play a critical role in training and testing DCNN models and improving performance. The ImageNet Large- Scale Visual Recognition Challenge (ILSVRC) announces that premier deep FR models were commonly trained on data larger than 0.5M images and 20K people Oloyede et al. (2020); RoyChowdhury et al. (2020). The training datasets are classified into two types, depth, and breadth RoyChowdhury et al. (2020). A depth dataset has a limited number of subjects but many images for each subject. It enforces the trained model to address a wide range of intraclass variations, such as lighting, age and pose. A breadth dataset contains many subjects but fewer images per subject. It ensures the trained models cover enough variable appearance of various people.

Table 3 covers the popular datasets used for face recognition, including the MS-Celeb-1M, CASIA-WebFace, VGGFace2, MegaFace, UTKFace, Facial Expression Comparison (FEC), and Labelled Faces in the Wild (LFW). These datasets are classified based on the dataset type (depth and breadth), the number of identities, and the total number of images. The numbers are inexact. The following sections explain the characteristics and objectives of these datasets and show the exact numbers of identities and images.

Table 3. Deep CNN Pretrained Models

Dataset Type	Reference	Dataset Name	#Identities	#Images
Depth	Song et al. (2020)	CASIA-WebFace	10.5k	500k
	Fariza et al. (2019)	CASIA-WebFace	10.1k	200k
	Singh et al. (2023)	VGGFace	9.1k	3.3M
	Abdelmaksoud et al. (2020)	LFW	5.7k	13.2k
Breadth	Peng et al. (2021)	MS-Celeb-1M	100k	10M
	Xu et al. (2021)	MageFace	672k	4.7M
	Vemulapalli and Agarwala (2019)	GFEC	500K	156K

5.1 Depth Datasets

Song et al. (2020) use CASIA-WebFace to train a DCCN model for similar face recognition. CASIA WebFace is the first public dataset consisting of 10,575 people, 494,414 face images collected from the web. Each person has 45 face images on average. The images are 250 x 250 pixels and taken with various light intensity levels, posture, and expression. The CASIA-WebFace dataset is typically used for scientific research of unconstrained face recognition; for face verification and face identification tasks. The authors note that the dataset includes some error labels and images; thus, dataset cleaning is required.

Fariza et al. (2019) utilize the UTKFace dataset to evaluate the performance of DCNN for age estimation of the range 1-100 years old. The UTKFace is a large-scale face dataset with an extended age range of 0 to 116. It includes 23,708 images with age, gender, and ethnicity annotations worldwide. The images are 240 x 240 pixels covering significant variations in pose, facial expression, illumination, occlusion, resolution. It is typically used for age estimation, age progression, and age regression tasks.

Singh et al. (2023) use the VGGFace dataset train DCNN for low resolution face recognition. The VGGFace dataset was developed by researchers at the Visual Geometry Group at the University of Oxford. It provides a large-scale training dataset of 3.31 million images of 9131 identities, with 362.6 images an average for each identity. The images are 240 x 240 pixels collected from Google Image Search. The VGGFace varies pose, age, illumination, ethnicity, and profession (e.g., actors, athletes, politicians). It is typically used for training and evaluating effective face recognition models and verification performance.

Abdelmaksoud et al. (2020) employ Labelled Faces in the Wild (LFW) dataset to train Super-Resolution Generative Adversarial Network (SRGAN) to overcome the low-resolution problem of face recognition with a single sample per person. The LFW dataset consists of 13,233 images of faces of 5749 identities collected from the web. The LFW is public and commonly used for face verification; however, it is not suitable to evaluate CNNs designed to recognize images with complicated conditions such as poor lighting, extreme pose, strong occlusions, low resolution. It is typically designed for research purposes of face recognition verification.

5.2 Breadth Datasets

Peng et al. (2021) compare the MS-Celeb-1M to other two datasets in the ethically problematic face and person recognition. Microsoft Corporation created the MS-Celeb-1M, consisting of 10 million face images collected from the Internet, including 100K identities; each identity has an average of 100 facial images. Each image is linked to an entity key identified by a unique key and associated with property information helps to conduct disambiguation and improve the recognition accuracy. The MS-Celeb-1M is a public dataset designed to develop face recognition for a large-scale classification problem.

Xu et al. (2021) use MageFace dataset to evaluate the performance of a training technique that speeds up capturing discriminative information for face recognition. The MageFace provides extensive training data to the research community. The MageFace is a public dataset containing 4.7 million images with 672K identities and a significant age variation, collected from Yahoo's Flickr. It evaluates the performance of face recognition algorithms in identification and verification.

Vemulapalli and Agarwala (2019) introduce Facial Expression Comparison (FEC) dataset used for analyzing and recognizing facial expression. The FEC is a large-scale face dataset with expression comparison annotations. Google Corporation designs it, consisting of 500k expression triplets (identities) with 156k face images and annotations that specify which two expressions in each triplet are most similar. The FEC is typically used for expression-based image retrieval, photo album summarization, emotion classification.

6. FACE RECOGNITION APPLICATIONS

Face recognition has received attention from research and commercial communities due to the wide range of real-world applications Adjabi et al. (2020); Ali et al. (2021). FR has been used in law enforcement, forensic investigation, controlling restricted access, social media, finance and banking, and other daily life applications such as unlocking smartphones, airline 7 checking-In and boarding, ordering in restaurants. The FR applications serve as face verification or identification. Face verification applications verify face information to registered facial data to confirm whether it is the person who says he/she is or not, while the FR identification

applications compare face information to a database of identities to determine the person's identity. Table 4 illustrates challenging FR applications and classifies them based on the application type (verification and identification) and the application domain.

Table 4. Face Recognition Applications

Application Type	Reference	Application Domain
Verification	Porselvi et al. (2021)	Banking & Security: Face-based access to Automatic Teller Machine (ATM)
	Kuchta et al. (2022)	Service: Face-based airlines check-in and boarding services
	Al-Amoudi et al. (2022)	Security: Face-based schools attendance system
Identification	Rikwith et al. (2021)	Security: Face recognition & fingerprint for Electronic Voting Machine
	Kute et al. (2019)	Forensic: Partial face images recognition for forensic applications
	Ortega-Delcampo et al. (2020)	Security: Detect morphing presentation attacks in border control system

6.1 Face Verification

Porselvi et al. (2021) use face recognition as facial identification for processing banking transactions of ATM system. The system compares the face scans with similar face information uploaded by the bank's personnel to verify the customer's identity. They use Haar Feature-based Cascade Classifiers for face detection, then pass on the face information to a deep belief network (DBN), one type of DCNN, for recognition. The process starts with the new user should register his/her face to get an account number; along with that, the user needs to fill in personal details like Username, Password, and Mail ID. The authors state the security advantages of using face recognition as facial identification for the banking system, reducing the danger of hackers, banking fraud, and misused once a user registers mobile is lost.

Kuchta et al. (2022) study the use of face recognition to increase the efficiency of the processes of check-in and boarding services. They analyzed ten face recognition systems, including Accenture, Aware, BioID, Certibio, Fulcrum Biometrics, Thales, HYPR, Idemia, Leidos, and NEC. The check-in and boarding services include passenger identity validation, baggage registration and handling, and seating assignment. The study shows that the check-in and boarding services provoke queues, requiring additional identity control processing. Therefore, using face recognition systems as identity control significantly reduces check-in queues, and the workforce is only required circumstances or when additional control is required.

Al-Amoudi et al. (2022) propose an automatic school attendance system using face recognition. The system consists of attendance, student profile, and training. A lecturer needs to take a photograph of the student and upload it to the system. The authors use Multi-Task Cascaded Convolutional Neural Network (MTCNN) for face detection and FaceNet for face recognition. They trained the system on 908 images of 21 students. The testing result showed 100% for face detection and 87.03% for face recognition.

6.2 Face Identification

Rikwith et al. (2021) present enhancement for Electronic Voting Machine (EVM) performance using biometric fingerprint and face recognition. The face recognition process includes collecting voters' image IDs, unique feature extraction, classification and storage in XML files, and voter prediction by matching input image features with the saved XML files. A voter's face is captured only if the face is well illuminated and classified using Eigen's face. The process runs until 50 viable images are collected from the person for data collection efficiency. The experiment shows that the system effectively allows only authenticated voting persons to be identified based on their fingerprint and face recognition and prevents unregistered voters from voting.

Kute et al. (2019) use partial face images available for forensic recognition purposes (so-called component-based face recognition). They utilize the transfer learning method using the knowledge gained from complete face images to classify components of the face. The essential face components used for recognition are ears, lips, and nose. They use Fisher's LDA, a transfer DCNN, to extract features and regularization block for probability minimization. They also utilize the K-nearest neighbor classifier for classification. The authors experimented with the system on the Faces94 dataset that contains face images of 153 individuals with 20 images per person. They also cropped various parts of a face from the Faces94 dataset, including half faces (left, right, upper, and lower half, and left, right, upper, and lower diagonal), nose, ears (left and right), and lips. The results show that nose features are better than lip and ear features for recognition accuracy.

Ortega-Delcampo et al. (2020) use face recognition for automated border control to prevent biometric attacks, which are presentation attacks. One of the biometric attacks is morphing, which is hard to detect. The authors use DCNN to de-morph a passport with a fake face image (morphed image). The process checks between the actual image of a person located in the automated border control system and the morphed image. An experiment was conducted on the FRAV-ABC database that consists of 1170 individuals, 640 females and 530 males. Each has two images, morphing and the actual one. Although the accuracy rate reached 98%, the equal error rate (EER) was low, which requires. The authors state that paying more attention to feature selection for CNN would improve the outcomes.

7. LIMITATIONS & RESEARCH DIRECTIONS

Face recognition technology has been adopted in real-world applications and shows remarkable success in well-controlled environments. However, face recognition is limited to accuracy and efficiency in real-life scenarios due to the face acquisition process with unconstrained environments, including illumination, pose variation, occlusion, face expression, plastic surgery, aging, and low resolution. The trained DCNN models perform well on the same dataset, but Recognition accuracy decreases when they perform on various datasets. Moreover, DCNN face recognition is limited to robustness for presentation attacks, such as masked face and digital manipulation attacks, threatening the security of face recognition systems.

7.1 Limitations

The set of 26 publications studied in this survey indicates that face recognition using DCNN is limited to:

- **Uncontrolled Environments:** Face images captured with low resolution, illumination, occlusion, and other detection issues, are difficult to detect; as a result, they fail to be recognized.
- **Masked Faces:** Many DCNN were developed for masked face recognition, especially with the COVID-19 pandemic; however, the classification accuracy is still low, and the equal error rate (EER) is unsuitable.
- **Face Expression:** Face emotions recognition is profitable; however, it lacks accuracy and efficiency, especially for face expression similarity.
- **Training Mechanism:** Training a DCNN model for face recognition lacks the diversity of the training datasets.
- **Partial Face Images:** forensic face recognition limits face classification and recognition due to the low effectiveness of the existing DCNN used for Partial face images classification.
- **Face Recognition Security Attacks:** Detection and recognize morphable faces is an open issue because the existing DCNN models provide unsuitable accuracy and high equal error rate.

These limitations are connected. Overcoming a limitation would help solve another issue of face recognition. For instance, increasing the face classification accuracy in uncontrolled environments improves the security attacks prevention for face recognition.

7.2 Research Directions

According to the face recognition limitations and the future works included in the studies covered in this survey, the further research directions are:

- **Detection Accuracy:** Detection of face images in uncontrolled environments requires advanced DCNN to be developed, trained, and evaluated in real-life scenarios.
- **Diversity of Datasets:** Diversifying datasets to train and test DCNN is necessary for face recognition.
- **Use other's Knowledge:** Transfer learning is practical to increase the effectiveness and efficiency of the DCNN for face recognition.
- **Standard Evaluation Metric:** Developing a standard evaluation metric for training and testing DCNN models of face recognition ensures the DCNN models' quality and reduces incidental ambiguity.
- **Security Attacks:** Increasing the precision over other evaluation factors of DCNN models might lower the equal error rates and tolerate the security attacks for face recognition.

8. CONCLUSION

This survey paper reviewed academic literature of 26 papers published from 2019 to early 2023 on using Deep Convolutional Neural Network (DCNN) for face recognition. A classification scheme that categorizes this literature was introduced. The classification scheme groups the 24 papers into four categories, DCNN architectures, pretrained models, training datasets, and applications.

The classical and modern DCNN architectures used for face recognition were explored, including hidden layers and types of activation and loss functions that distinguish these architectures. Popular pretrained models including VGG19, ResNet50, Inception-v3 (GoogLeNet), EfficientNet-B3, and MobileFaceNet were explored, and their classification accuracy was discussed.

The survey also covers the popular datasets used for training and testing face recognition models, including the MS-Celeb-1M, CASIA-WebFace, VGGFace2, MegaFace, UTKFace, Facial Expression Comparison (FEC), and Labelled Faces in the Wild (LFW).

Critical applications that used DCNN face verification and identification, such as ATM banking, forensic investigation, airline checking-In and boarding, and electronic voting machine, were discussed and evaluated. Finally, DCNN face recognition limitations were explained, and further research directions were highlighted.

Using DCNN for face recognition is promising; however, accuracy and efficiency are limited, especially in real-life scenarios. It is due to the lack of training on practical and diverse training datasets. The DCNN face recognition is also limited to robustness for presentation attacks, introducing security concerns.

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